

The ways to reflect affective emotions (anger, joy, horror, admiration) and their expression in literary texts

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Abstract: The first part of the abstract of this paper demonstrates how understanding the variety of ways that emotional responses modulate ongoing attention leads to what I refer to as the puzzle of emotional attention, which is based on the idea that various emotions (such as fear, happiness, disgust, admiration, etc.) have various attentional profiles. The mystery surrounds why this is the case, and a solution entails illuminating why certain emotions have the various attentional profiles that they do. After that, it gives an explanation of the functional roles played by various emotions in relation to their evaluative themes, further illuminating their individual attentional profiles and resolving the conundrum of emotional attention. Then it describes how these attentional profiles are represented in the nature of emotional experience and its.

Key words; fear, happiness, disgust, admiration have different attentional profiles

Introduction

Emotion and attention may be tightly related, according to empirical studies and daily experience. Much of what catches our attention outside of controlled experimental environments, in the "natural environment," does so because it has emotional importance. Footnote1 Consider the case below. I'm taking a leisurely stroll in the park when a barking Alsatian comes darting at me from nowhere, and I'm instantly seized with terror. Unwillingly focusing on the emotionally salient object is a component of my terror response. This is not all, though. The emotional response further modulates the character and direction of ongoing attention once attention is so captured. As the dog gets closer, I 'fixate' on its movements, maintaining attention on it, and for as long as this dog remains a threat to me, it *consumes* my (ongoing) attention, resulting in a *narrowing* of my 'attentional gaze'.

We can discern two essential ways in which emotion and attention interact based on examples like the ones mentioned above. In the beginning, emotionally charged stimuli merely passively draw attention. In many situations, this takes the shape of what is referred to as "selective attention" in philosophical and psychological literature. Footnote2 This typically manifests as a diachronic attention shift, involving "overt" attention in the sense of moving one's sensory apparatus (typically a sense organ) to achieve the best orientation for learning about the "selected" object (for instance, moving one's head so that the object stimulates the fovea, the area of the eye that produces the highest degree of visual acuity. There is another effect after this attention-getting quality that characterizes our emotional responses. The emotional state (together with the continued awareness of the emotional

stimuli) further regulates the way we are attending to the object of our emotion, or as I will put it, modulates ongoing attention, as we saw in the example of the fear-response above. This paper's first objective is to demonstrate how understanding the variety of ways that emotional responses modulate ongoing attention leads to what I refer to as the puzzle of emotional attention, which is based on the idea that various emotions (such as fear, happiness, disgust, admiration, boredom, etc.) have various attentional profiles. The mystery is why this is the case, and one way to solve it is to explain why different emotions have different attentional profiles (Sect. 2). Then, I give an explanation of the functional functions of various emotions in relation to their evaluative themes, which clarifies and further explains the various attentional profiles of various emotions (Sect. 3). Following that, I outline how such attentional profiles are reflected in the character of emotional experience and its attentional phenomenology (Sect. 4). The resulting picture is a more detailed account of the connections between emotion and attention than is currently on offer in the philosophical literature, and a substantive account of the distinctive attentional profiles of different emotions.

Let me first discuss the overarching rationale for concentrating on the function of attention in particular in emotion. As you will see in what follows, concentrating on the unique attentional profiles of various emotions gives us additional criteria for individuating various emotional kinds. In relation to this, the attentional focus enables us to emphasize the distinctive functional roles of emotions and groups of emotions in connection with their "evaluative themes," tying these together in what I hope to demonstrate is illuminating for understanding emotions and distinct emotion-types. Last but not least, describing how the attentional profiles of emotion impact the nature of emotional experience and its attentional phenomenology promises to illuminate emotional phenomenology further.

Methods and analysis

Returning to our distinctions in the introduction, we might be tempted to think that we can capture the way emotion affects attention by modelling all cases after fear-responses (or consonant negative emotions). This would run as follows: in any given emotional response, there is an initial instance of attention capture followed by a maintaining of attention of the emotional object, which involves a 'narrowing' of attentional focus. Insofar as this kind of view has it that the structure of attention in emotional response is 'capture' followed by 'consumption', we can call this (following Michael Brady) the 'capture-consumption' model.^{Footnote5}

However, this view looks to be problematic. Reflection on everyday experience and a growing body of empirical research suggests that positive emotions, such as happiness and joy, have effects on ongoing attention (after initial attention capture) which are significantly different from the kind of consumption of attention that is paradigmatic of fear-responses

(and consonant emotions). For example, happiness leads to a widening rather than a narrowing of attention, which in many cases shifts attentional focus away from the initial emotional stimuli. Footnote6 Also, the character of ongoing attention in some appreciation emotions involves a ‘zooming out’ effect, focusing on global features of the object which contrasts with the ‘zooming in’ effect we see in the case of fear-responses. Emotion psychologist Nico Frijda describes the kinds of attentional modulations connected with the emotional-response of joy in similar terms: ‘it is in part aimless, unasked-for readiness to engage in whatever interaction presents itself and in part readiness to engage in enjoyments’. Footnote7 These descriptions are somewhat vague, but they nonetheless suggest that the ‘capture-consumption’ model involves an unwarranted generalisation from how attention works in the case of fear (and similar negative emotions).

Whether this is a plausible thing to say about the specific attentional profile of happiness, and whether it has the means to capture the subtlety of the way different emotions affect attention—see Sect. 3.2 for a somewhat different picture—we might ask the following question. Are there forms of *ongoing attention* in certain emotions which are plausibly constitutive in Brady’s sense—that is not merely being the downstream focusing on objects strictly ‘other’ than the of the original emotional event—but nonetheless don’t involve the *persistence of attentional focus* which is the hallmark of the ‘capture-and-consumption’ model? Arguably there are at least two key examples. First consider disgust: disgust, which is standardly classified as a negative emotional-response—and so one which we might expect to involve the kind of narrowing of attentional focus and persistence of focus—typically has an effect on the ongoing modulation of attention which involves *turning away* from the ‘offensive stimuli’, such that there is no narrowing of attentional focus on the object of the emotional-response, but rather a modulation of attention which seems geared towards *not* keeping attention fixed on the object or event that elicited it. The more precise attentional profile of disgust will concern us later, but it exhibits a ‘constitutive’ attentional profile, that doesn’t fit the capture-consumption model. Alternatively, consider the way boredom exhibits ‘attentional drift’, in which attention is not widened per se, but rather disperses or perhaps it just ‘lost’ (rather than say ‘consequentially’ focusing on some other object). Indeed, the feeling of a *loss or scattering of attention* characteristic of certain forms of boredom points to an interesting attentional phenomenon, which is sufficiently distinctive of that type of emotion, and which the capture-consumption looks too simplistic to capture.

The exposition so far should have made it clear that my focus is in the modulation of ongoing attention in emotional responses as it relates to the objects or stimuli of the emotional response. In other words, the emphasis is on the modulation of our continuing relationship with the emotional objects. Footnote15 Note that one can pause to consider if it makes sense to speak of an ongoing relationship to the object of emotion in the examples listed when continuing attentional focus is enlarged or widened, such as in the pleasant feeling of happiness. It is debatable whether it does or not because continuous attention may be regulated in enjoyment to only slightly ‘wander away’ from the initial emotional object

while constantly maintaining. In any case, the attentional phenomena and ongoing attentional modulations I will be concerned with are not merely the ‘narrow case’, exemplified in the fear-response case, of ongoing *selective attention* or ‘fixation’, but will be seen to cover range of distinctive attentional phenomena and modulations, such as *mental turning away*, *vigilance*, *mental drift*, *dwelling*, *ruminating* and others. In this context it is also worth noting that my focus will principally be on detailing *actual changes* in the character and direction of ongoing attention in emotional episodes, as manifest in the emotional episodes themselves, rather than *mere dispositions* to such changes (this will be clear in the foregoing analysis; see .

Conclusion

Let me surmise what has been achieved in this paper. We began by outlining the puzzle of emotional attention. I then argued that a plausible solution to that puzzle appeals to emotions’ functional roles as tied to specific evaluative themes, which has implications for what attentional modulations would best serve those functional roles. Several concrete cases were considered, and the account was shown to be a promising way of understanding why distinct emotions have the attentional profiles they do and what those attentional profiles amount to. In the final section, I sketched how such attentional profiles ‘leave their mark’ on and connect with emotional phenomenology. What we have therefore been provided with is a richer account of the relation between emotion and attention than has so far been offered in the philosophical literature, which will be of use to those seeking to better understand the connections between emotion and attention.

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